

CREE Timber-Hybrid System

Versatile prefabricated building construction

A sophisticated hybrid construction system for high rise buildings, connecting modular prefabricated components to an optimized planning and construction process in a constantly evolving collaborative model. A cutting-edge solution for the new digital era.

Highlights of innovative features

- The modular system uses a predefined grid of prefabricated hybrid slab panels to which the various other components - walls, ceilings, facades, etc. - are added with large flexibility of the layout.
- Based on a full digital twin, the integrated planning and delivery allows to optimize all flows of materials, information and processes. This leads to tremendous potential savings on cost, transport, material, time and carbon emissions.
- Open functional spaces with a biophilic atmosphere provide a healthy office environment for well-being of employees.
- Life Cycle Management ensures highly energy efficient buildings.

Next generation buildings require flexibility and full control over the entire life cycle from construction, operation and end-of-life. Integrating all phases into digital collaboration models delivers the future of aesthetics and performance in building design.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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